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Pattern of short-range connections between cortical layers are sometimes described as canonical circuits. Their anatomical correlate is thought to be the cortical column – a functional subunit of cortical processing. Discuss evidence for and against the concept that cerebral cortex is a repeating assemblage of processing units.

Summary

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1. Introduction

<<A cortical column is a module in the neocortex, **approximately 300-600 micron** in diameter, **composed of many mini columns** couple by short-range horizontal connections. Neurons within a column often share dynamic response properties. In general, a column is a part of a continuous sheet of neocortex, where the **boundaries** of individual columns **cannot be determined by anatomy alone**, although there are **exceptions such as the barrel field columns in the rodent neocortex**. >>

[Sean Hill, 2014]

This definition of cortical column is taken from Sean Hill, the co-Director of the Blue Brain Project.

The Blue Brain Project (bluebrain.epfl.ch) is an ambitious program launched in

2005 by the Brain and Mind Institute of the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne(EPFL), based on the idea of constructing a large-scale network model that simulate the basic components of the architecture of the brain in order to recreate the functional properties emerging from it (Markram 2006; Meyer 2013).

The first part of the project aims the “detailed reconstruction of a neocortical column” - the so-called Blue Column- of a 2 week-old-rat somatosensory cortex, as an “ideal starting point from which the column can be ‘matured’ to study development, ‘transformed’ to study regional specialization and ‘evolved’ to study evolution of the neocortex” (Markram 2006). The final goal of the project is the simulation of a whole neocortex (Human brain Project). Beyond the reductionist approach that frames this study, there is also the strong assumption that the neocortex is “stereotypically organized” with “invariance in structure and function” (Markram 2002). But how well-grounded is this assumption?

In bold character I underlined a few key words that in my opinion synthesize very well the main issues of such a hot topic like cortical columns.

In this essay I will review the major discoveries that lead to the statements on which the BBP is founded, trying to shed light on the discrepancies.

Then, I’ll show data from recent experimental studies arguing against and in favor of the idea that the cerebral cortex is made of “repeatedly occurring identical cortical circuits” (expression of Meyer, 2013) and two possible approaches to look at the problem: one on one side, emphasizing the structural aspect of the columns, on the other side the functional properties (§ 3.2, 3.3).

2. Cortical columns: the history of an ‘ontological commitment’

The idea of a vertical column-like organization of cell bodies in the cerebral cortex was already in the air during the golden era of classical neuroanatomy (Rakic 2008).

The first conjecture of an ‘elementary unit’ represented by vertical chains of neurons, through the six layers in the neocortex, can be ascribed to Lorente de Nó (1902-1990), a famous disciple of Ramón y Cajal (1852-1934) who studied the mouse cerebral cortex.

However, the concept of functional columnarity of the cortex dates back to the ‘50s.

Fig. 1. Images showing the neocortical column (NCC) microcircuit in various stages of reconstruction.

[Markram 2006]

Exactly 60 years ago, in the 1955, Mountcastle through single neuron recording experiments in cats and monkeys describes the columnar organization of the somatosensory cortex. Making perpendicular electrode penetrations he saw that neurons sharing the receptive field location were segregated in the same block of tissue ('modality-specificity' columns). Those cells responses would abruptly change from one sub modality to the other, if the angle of the penetration inclined. As 'elementary building blocks of the sensory cortices', the cortical columns appeared to have a discrete structure, with sharp boundaries inserted in an 'intricate mosaic-like fashion'. The first official definition of a column was then: "elementary unit of organization in the somatic cortex made up of a vertical group of cells extending through all the cellular layers" (Mountcastle 1957 in Horton and Adams 2005).

Soon, this discovery led to "a paradigm for probing the functional architecture of any area of the neocortex" (Da Costa and Martin 2010), initiating studies to map receptive fields in many other cortical areas.

The heritage of the cortical column was taken in the '60s by Hubel and Wiesel whose notable studies in the cat primary visual cortex -worth winning the Nobel Prize- seemed to find in the orientation columns the confirmation of Mountcastle's hypothesis: "discrete organization of cells, each aggregation being separated from its neighbors by vertical wall that intersect the surface (or a given layer) in a mosaic" (Da Costa and Martin 2010)

However, later data from recording in macaque's striate cortex challenged the notion of discrete borders in columns: orientation columns were 'borderless' and the optimal orientation tuning varied smoothly (Horton and Adams 2005; Da Costa and Martino 2010).

Columns were not like 'cylindrical pillars' but looked more like 'swirling slabs'. But the concept was already well established in the scientific community and there was no way other than "either [...] broaden the definition of the column or decide that the system is not strictly columnar" (Horton and Adams 2005). They decided to keep the belief.

Almost simultaneously, another idea was germinating in the field of developmental neurobiology: the 'ontogenetic columns'. Besides the name, the word was used to designate the set of cortical neurons clones originating from the same single neuronal progenitor and 'migrating' foetal development from the white matter into the cortical layers, in a perfect radial pattern (radial unit hypothesis formulated by Rakic: Horton and Adams 2005; Rakic 2008).

No relationship between these kind of columns (much smaller than the one proposed by Mountcastle's) and the functional columns of the mature adult was ever proved, but still attempts to make connections between the two were made both by Rakic and Mountcastle. This led to the replacement of the old concept of 'column' with the brand new 'minicolumn', an even more 'basic modular unit of the neocortex forming the column' by aggregation with short-range horizontal connections, a concept essentially created to fit the new theory but with no convincing evidence supporting it.

Another highly influential study, strictly connected to the discover of cortical columns, was the one made by Rockel et al. (1980) which state the intrinsic uniformity in structure of the neocortex. Through a comparative study in all mammalian species and cytoarchitectonic areas (except from area 17 of the visual cortex in primates), the authors claim to have found that the same number of neurons (110) is constant in all areas and in all species. Those findings have been widely criticized by further studies that pointed out problems regarding both methods and data (see later): the arbitrary selection of the cortical column -from which the number of neurons was estimated - was considered dubious itself (Rakic 2008). But the basic idea was so appealing that it couldn't be uprooted anymore: despite everything the paper was cited more than 500 times so far.

2.1. Too many entities for this world

In spite of all the evident incongruities between physiological results and morphology, Mountcastle's 'copy-left' product was fatally successful as a general principle for a unified understanding of the cortical function and the column 'trade-mark' was recognizable in many other subsequent studies.

Nevertheless, the (mis)use of the term 'column' can sound misleading to a non specialist, since, vertical or radial iterative columnar organization aside, many other heterogeneous characteristics are listed as good candidates to define it: cell constellation, pattern of connectivity, myelin content, staining property, magnitude of gene expression, functional properties (Rakic 2008).

Hence, the same big family of columns would pool together: ocular dominance columns, orientation columns, hypercolumns and color columns (only for the primary visual cortex); columns in ipsilateral and callosal projections in the frontal lobe (Bugbee & Goldman-Rakic 1983 in Horton and Adams 2005 e Rakic 2008); the so-called mini columns; the barrel fields columns; the ontogenetic columns.

Undoubtedly, there is no general agreement about any aspect of this entity.

Indeed, as we will see later, it seems more like the word 'column' was used in its 'historical or metaphorical sense' (Da Costa and Martin 2010) lacking an univocal correspondence between the concept and the real entities that are supposed to lie under its domain.

3. When structure doesn't meet function

As we saw the original meaning for cortical column was a functional entity (Lund 2003). Infact, as Da Costa and Martino points out 'no one has seen the anatomy of a column' (Da Costa and Martin 2010): all we know is a 'remarkable constancy in the receptive field properties' *inferred* from perpendicular recordings in clusters of neurons of the same kind of stimulus. The structural architecture was hard to define and obliged researchers to an expansion of the original definition to include more nuanced structures. Consequently the term is abused in the structural sense such that any vertically organized pattern can be promoted as a column, as long as it shows those features. Focusing on the structure, one loses sight of the function in a process whose extreme version can be found in the 'reverse engineering' of the Blue Brain Project.

3.1. The barrel cortex case

Reconciling the structure of the neocortex with its functional layout seems to be the biggest challenge of the past half century.

At the very beginning of this essay we mentioned the historical antecedent of the cortical column, accredited to Lorente De Nò's studies on the rodent barrelfield.

Also in our quotation from the *Enciclopedia of Computational Neuroscience* the barrel cortex is regarded as a virtuous exception of columnar organization (see also other studies mentioned in Horton and Adams 2005), because the whiskers are discretely represented.

Among all the cortical columns candidates appeared in our roll call (§2.1), then, the barrel cortex wins as ideal example “where both anatomical and functional column is well defined” (Hill 2014), conforming to Mountcastle original definition (Horton and Adams 2005).

From this point of view most of the research conducted in the last ten years has given a strong emphasis to the study of rat somatosensory cortex, appointed as the preferred brain area (Horton and Adams 2005; Markram 2006; Meyer 2013; Hill 2014). In particular, the Blue Brain project, despite the claims of building a model that can be applied to the whole brain, has been investing all his efforts in just a specific region of a specific mammal (rodent), discarding other species usually studied in this kind of research (cats and primates).

But the barrel cortex is nothing else that a *topographic representation* of the rodent whiskers in the somatosensory cortex (Fig. 2.), like the retinotopic map in primary visual cortex or the representation of digits in humans and primates in the somatotopic map. Apart from the discreteness of the shape, “cortical barrels are not really columns”(Horton and Adams 2005) since “they differ from the functional columns seen in cats and monkeys” (Da Costa and Martin 2010).

However, it's curious that from Hubel and Wiesel onwards, scientists have fallen in this trap citing the barrel cortex as an ‘unusual case’ instead of recognizing the misnomer. Considering the barrel cortex as an example of cortical columns, rather than being a ‘matter of taste and semantics’ (Hubel and Wiesel, 1974a in Da Costa and Martino 2010), seems actually just a convenient affiliation to square the circle.

Fig. 2. Whisker-specific laminar cellular organization of rat vibrissal cortex. (A) Tangential and semicoronal (B) view of all neuron somata in the vibrissal cortex of one animal. [Meyer 2013]

3.2. The structural level

The concept of uniformity of the cortex across modalities, species and during evolution of neocortical expansion (Rakic 2008), introduced by Rockle & colleagues in the '80s, owes its success also for being feasibly adopted in computational models, like the BBP.

One of the predictions of the model is that the expansion takes place through the addition of columns with a constant number of neurons.

A recent study by Herculano-Houzel and colleagues (2008) test whether the average of number of neurons (N) beneath a unit of cortical surface (A) is invariant across primate species (ratio N/A remains constant).

To do that they establish that the number of neurons (N) is equal to the product of surface area (A), cortical thickness (T), and neuronal density (D): $N = A \times T \times D$ (Fig.3). For the ratio N/A to be constant across species, they expect an inverse proportionality between cortical thickness and neuronal density, since $N/A = D \times T$.

Fig.3. “The average number of neurons beneath the cortical surface (N/A) varies across species as a linear function of the product of neuronal density and cortical thickness (D x T) as expected from the equation $N = A \times D \times T$. Points represent the average values for each of the 10 species analyzed.” [Herculano-Houzel 2008]

However, results show that cortical thickness doesn't covary with neuronal density (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. “Cortical thickness does not correlate with neuronal density in the cerebral cortex. Points represent the average values for each of the 10 species analyzed”. [Herculano-Houzel 2008]

Since the cortical thickness (T) and cortical density (D) are not inversely proportional, their product is not constant and consequently also the ratio N/A is not constant.

These results are questioned by Carlo and Stevens (2012) who criticize the methods to average the number of neurons in that study. Indeed, according to Rockle’s study striate cortex has a higher density of neurons in respect of other cortical areas but Herculano-Houzel et al. don’t exclude area V1 from the estimation of N/A . However, the authors themselves had recognized this possibility (Herculano 2008): if such a bias in the average number of neurons beneath the surface does occur, “making it appear variable across species”, this variation would be much smaller than the one found across species. The striate cortex, representing 20% of the entire cortex and containing two times higher neuronal density than the rest of the cortex, would account for a 30% variation in the average number of neurons against the 3 times variation found across species (Herculano-Houzel et al. 2008).

Replicating Rockel et al.’s experiments with modern stereological methods, Carlo and Stevens’ (2012) study instead comes to the same conclusions that the number of neurons in a unit of neocortical surface is constant in four different areas (excluding area V1) of four different mammalian species (mouse, rat, cat, monkey). It’s not clear, in this study, what the authors define by ‘constant’: the results they report (fig. 5) show that the total number of cells (neurons plus glia) covary with the cortical thickness, increasing (fig. A); same for the number of glia in relation with the cortical thickness. They say, though, that the cortical thickness variation is “unrelated to the species or area studied”, “because the cortical thicknesses of the various species are overlapping”, but they don’t report any value for the cortical thicknesses among the species to evaluate that there is no statistical difference.

Fig. 5. “Data presented for four cortical areas and for monkey, cat, rat, and mouse. [...]

(A) Number of neurons plus glia under 1 mm² of cortical surface. [...] This regression line is significantly different from zero ($P = 0.01$). (B) Number of neurons under 1 mm² of cortical surface. [...] This slope is not significantly different from zero ($P = 0.63$). (C) Number of glial cells under 1 mm² of cortical surface. The regression line has a slope [...] significantly different from zero ($P = 0.0001$).” [Carlo and Stevens 2012]

Not to mention the fact that it's absolutely obscure how they estimate the number of neurons and cells under 1 mm square.

Moreover, first in the experimental procedures they list the areas under study

(motor, somatosensory, parietal and temporal cortices), while later they affirm they are comparing the data of thickness for the same three areas reported by Rockle et al., which are “parietal, motor and primary visual” (in brackets in the text) - with the visual area supposed to be excluded from the study.

If we (wrongly) assume that cortical barrel columns are functional columns (§ 3.1), we can recall a recent study run by Meyer et al.(2013) which inquire exactly if the barrel columns “represent *stereotypic* anatomical correlates of functional columns”, thus following that cortical organization is structurally uniform. Using different methods than stereology, they found that the average number of all neurons (excitatory and inhibitory) per barrel column increases by around 2.5 fold from columns in the dorsal facial whisker (A-row) to columns in the ventral whiskers (E-row) concomitantly with the column volume (fig. 6, A and B).

Fig. 6. (A) “Average volume per barrel column based on the four vibrissal cortices analyzed, showing a significant increase from the A- to the E-row. (B) Average number of all neurons (excitatory and inhibitory) per barrel column, increasing from the A- to the E-row concomitantly with the column volume.” [Meyer 2013]

The conclusions driven by the authors are that barrel field “reflects the degree of similarity in sensory input and not columnar and/or cortical uniformity principles”.

Fig. 6. (C) “The average neuron density (excitatory and inhibitory) per barrel column is constant across the barrel field and larger than septal neuron density (box). (D) The average fraction of inhibitory neurons (IN) is similar across the barrel field and does not differ between columns and the septum (box)”. [Meyer 2013]

However, they don't comment the fact that the average neuron density is constant (Fig. 6. C and D), which could be a contrargument in favor of the structural uniformity.

3.3. The functional level: throwing away the structure

Da Costa and Martino 2010 end their review *Whose cortical column would that be?* proposing a concept to replace the cortical column, the 'canonical circuit', a model based on the statistics of connections between the different cell types: "this view of the responses of cortical neurons might solve the riddle of the elusive and illusive anatomical column, since [...] one should not expect either to ring anatomical boundaries of the column" (Da Costa and Martin 2010).

Still the idea of a repeated canonical circuit lives. What changes is that the functional architecture of the columnar model from static becomes dynamic and it is not supported anymore by a defined morphological layout.

Recently, Narayanan et al. (2015), although still sticking on the idea that the vertical patterns in vibrissa cortex can be studied as 'elementary functional units of sensory cortex', reveal how important the horizontal connections are, requiring that the concept of cortical columns [...] as the "minimal entity of cortical processing has to be extended at the next level of structural representation to IC-units (i.e. *intracortical*).

A last study that I would like to mention is the one by Bachatene et colleagues (2015). After having talked a lot about the rat somatosensory cortex, I would like to go back to the first observations in the cat visual cortex made by Hubel and Wiesel. That the concept of orientation column was an artifact was already pointed out (§2). Here a recent study on adult cats breaks down the idea that orientation selectivity rests on an inflexible columnar organization, where just the neurons segregated inside it respond to stimuli presented in their receptive field (RF).

Their results show that, after applying an adapter, even neurons belonging to non-adapted RF sites, located far from the adapted RF, shift their respective orientation tuning curves for novelty stimuli (fig. 7a and b).

This for the authors implies that the orientation columns, traditionally thought to be a stable structure in the visual system after the critical period, are actually really variable domains.

Fig. 7a. On the left, the respective positions of three receptive fields. Only receptive field Was adapted. On the right, site A, the adapted RF. Downward red arrow heads indicate the adapting orientation in all the figures. Tuning curves pre- and post-adaptation are illustrated for each stimulated site. [Bachatene et al. 2015]

Fig. 7b. Non-adapted sites B and C showing tuning shifts. [Bachatene et al. 2015]

Their conclusion is that “orientation columns transcend anatomy, and are functionally dynamic entities” and that “columnar organization is a *processing unit* rather than an anatomically based structure”.

4. Conclusions

Ten years after the review by Horton and Adams (2005) and the almost proclaimed ‘death of cortical columns’ (Da Costa and Martin 2010), attempts to save the concept are still made, dismantling it more and more in its bases.

Maybe as a reaction to the mainstream tendency of turning inside out the anatomy of putative columnar organization for the quest of the emergent functionality (see BBP), a lot of studies are flourishing around the notion that the cortical columns are instead functional entities without recognizable structures.

We saw two branches of the debate, with recent studies disputing either against (Herculano-Houzel 2008; Meyer 2013) or in favour (Carlo and Stevens 2012; Bachatene et al. 2015) the idea of the brain as a stereotypical ‘assemblage of processing units’ ‘with more or less sound arguments.

Neither side has reached a conclusive point in the debate, with weaknesses in both of the factions (that Carlo and Steven 2012 ironically define ‘lumpers’ and ‘splitters’). Which means we are still firmly far from the idealistic dream of re-building intelligence playing with the brain structures like Lego bricks.

References

- Bachatene, L., Bharmauria, V., Cattan, S., Rouat, J. & Molotchnikoff, S. (2015). Reprogramming of orientation columns in visual cortex: a domino effect. *Sci. Rep.* 5, 9436.
- Carlo, C. N., Stevens, C. F. (2012). Structural uniformity of neocortex, revisited. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*, 110(4), 1488-1493.
- Da Costa, N. M., Martin, K. A. C. (2010). Whose cortical column would that be? *Frontiers in Neuroanatomy*, 4(16), 1-10.
- Herculano-Housel S, Collins CE, Wang P, Kaas J (2008) The basic nonuniformity of the cerebral cortex. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*, 105, 12593–12598.
- Hill, S. (2014). Cortical columns, models of. *Encyclopedia of Computational Neuroscience*, 1-4.
- Horton, J. C., Adams, D. L., (2005). The cortical column: a structure without a function. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B*, 360, 837-862.
- Lund, J. S., Angelucci, A., Bressloff, P. C. (2003). Anatomical Substrates for Functional Columns in Macaque Monkey Primary Visual Cortex. *Cerebral Cortex*, 12(15–24), 1047–3211.
- Markram, H. (2006), Blue brain project. *Nat Rev Neurosci.*, 7(2), 153–160.
- Meyer, H. S. et al. (2013). Cellular organization of cortical barrel columns is whisker-specific. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*, 110 (47), 19113–19118.
- Narayanan , R. T. et al. (2015). Beyond columnar organization: cell type and target layer-specific principles of horizontal axon projection pattern in rat vibrissal cortex. *Cerebral cortex*, 1-19.
- Rakic, P., (2008). Confusing cortical columns. *Proceeding of the National Academy of Sciences*, 105(34), 12009-12100.
- Rockel, A. J., Hiorns, R. W., Powell, T.P. (1980), The basic uniformity structure of the neocortex. *Brain*, 103(2), 221-44.
- Sillberberg, G., Gupta, A., Markram, H. (2002), Stereotypy in neocortical microcircuits. *Trends Neurosci.*, 25(5), 227-30.